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REHABILITATION OF CANCER PATIENTS: CURRENT DIRECTIONS OF RECOVERY TREATMENT

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Abstract

Today, issues related to restorative treatment in patients with malignant neoplasms continue to remain pressing, since this section of oncology is the most labor-intensive and requires an integrated approach, and the concept of quality of life is increasingly appearing in clinical studies along with survival. This paper describes modern directions of rehabilitation of cancer patients with different localization of the tumor process. The currently available methods of rehabilitation treatment and scientific directions that require further research to improve the quality of life of this contingent of patients are described. The use of a comprehensive program of medical rehabilitation in cancer patients will restore their vital conditions as much as possible and will optimize the processes of physical, psychological and social adaptation of these patients, which is the main task of oncology and rehabilitation today.

Keywords: oncology, rehabilitation, quality of life.

High rates of incidence of malignant tumors and a priori aggressive treatment methods and, often, the prevalence of the oncological process itself lead to disability, requiring rehabilitation measures. In this regard, such a section of clinical oncology as the rehabilitation of cancer patients must be on the same level with modern treatment, diagnosis and prevention of cancer [1,2].

It is important to especially emphasize that rehabilitation measures begin not after the patient develops various kinds of physical and psycho-emotional dysfunctions as a result of specialized treatment and (or) complications of the tumor process, but already from the moment the diagnosis of a malignant neoplasm is made. At the same time, patients registered with an oncologist often experience various kinds of functional disorders that affect their quality of life and ability to work. For example, physical disorders may include fatigue, decreased muscle strength, cognitive dysfunction, paraesthesia, or eating problems, while mental

symptoms may include anxiety, depression, fear of relapse, or insomnia. In this regard, the role of rehabilitation doctors and the importance of specialists with the skills of professional assessment and therapy in oncology services in this situation can hardly be overestimated [3].

One of the important aspects of complex rehabilitation of cancer patients is the use of drug correction of the psycho-emotional state of cancer patients, which previously received little attention. It is clear that oncologists and rehabilitation specialists take on this difficult role, but in some, quite common cases, additional drug support for the patient's psyche is required [4,5].

Thus, Taiwanese researchers Cheng-Hsu Wang et al. [6] not only analyzed, but also proved that the need for psychotropic drugs depends on the nosological form of the tumor. They analyzed data from 35,137 cancer patients from Taiwan's National Health Insurance database over 2.5 years. Among those patients who survived for at least 6 months, every fifth (20.9%) used

psychotropic drugs: patients were most often prescribed sedatives (14.3%), then antidepressants (5.5%), anxiolytics (3.6%) and antipsychotics (2.7%). Lung cancer, prostate cancer and oral cancer showed a statistically significant association with regular drug use during the first six months after diagnosis. And among patients who survived for at least 2.5 years, 4.8% still use psychotropic medications on a regular basis.

Catherine L. Granger et al. [7] found through a systematic review of articles using the electronic databases Medline, Cinahl, Embase, Scopus and Cochrane that despite evidence and existing guidelines for physical activity in patients with lung cancer, it is hardly implemented in clinical practice. This systematic review of the literature showed that the challenges of adequate physical rehabilitation of patients with lung cancer are multifaceted and involve various factors. These include patient-level factors such as symptoms, comorbidities, sedentary lifestyle, mood and fear, and environmental factors. These factors should be taken into account to determine and develop a treatment and rehabilitation program for these patients.

In addition, very little attention is often paid to the fact that the main moral burden when caring for cancer patients falls, of course, on their loved ones. And, unfortunately, according to Swedish researchers Ji J. et al. [8] spouses of cancer patients who provide care are at increased risk of coronary heart disease and stroke. This is necessary to know for the correct approach to correcting the psychological state of not only the patient himself, but also their relatives (family rehabilitation).

At the same time, Badr H. et al. [9] found a low level of self-efficacy and a high level of distress when independently caring for patients with advanced lung cancer. The authors, based on experimental studies in which 39 patients took part, developed a program to coordinate care and train care skills for such patients. The program was based on self-determination theory. Participants reported significant reductions ($p < 0.0001$) in depression, anxiety, and caregiving burden, increased caregiver competence, and caregiver autonomy to provide care compared to usual care.

Similar results were obtained in their study by Kim Y. et al. [10]. The authors note that the difficulty of psychological adaptation of relatives in families in which there is a cancer patient and the lack of social support are the main predictors of the development of major depressive disorders, even 3 years after diagnosis. At the same time, programs for adaptation to long-term care are crucial for the possibility of long-term (5-year results were taken into account) active care for the patient.

In addition, El-Jawahri A. et al. [11] found that patients' inadequate perception of their prognosis regarding cancer affects many of their decisions about medical care. However, the relationships between prognostic perception, quality of life, and patient mood itself are not yet fully understood. They stated the fact that, although patients wanted to know detailed information about their illness, half incorrectly perceived the fact that the prognosis in their situation was favorable. Of the 50 patients included in the study, 38 (76%) wanted

to know as many details as possible about their diagnostic procedures and treatments. However, 25 of 50 patients (50%) stated that their goal was to "cure cancer," and only 10 of 49 patients (20%) reported that they had completely "put their fate in the hands of their oncologist." Patients who accepted their illness as a death sentence reported lower quality of life ($p = 0.005$) and higher levels of anxiety ($p = 0.003$) compared to those who did not perceive themselves as terminally ill. The authors established a direct connection between accurate prognostic perception and the quality of life of patients. Therefore, interventions aimed at improving understanding of disease prognosis provide adequate psychosocial support for these people.

Any methods, as we all understand perfectly well, should be used to alleviate the condition of cancer patients and restore their well-being. Such methods include art therapy, which, of course, belongs to non-traditional methods of influence, but with a comprehensive program of restorative treatment it shows its effectiveness.

Lee J. et al. [12] decided to evaluate the effect of art therapy using paintings by famous artists on the manifestation of long-term chronic stress (distress) in cancer patients receiving radiation therapy. The level of anxiety, depression and symptoms associated with the manifestation of the cancer itself were assessed. The authors conducted a prospective study that included 24 cancer patients with various forms of malignant neoplasms who received radiation therapy. Art therapy took place in two parts, including 4 sessions of a famous painting course and 4 sessions of works of art of the creative generation; these sessions were held twice a week for four weeks. Distress was assessed using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS), and the Edmonton Symptom Assessment Scale (ESAS) at three assessment points: before the start of art therapy, after the fourth session, and then after the eighth session. Art therapy. It was found that of the 24 patients included in the study, 20 patients (83%) completed all eight sessions. At the same time, the authors note a significant and even significantly significant decrease in indicators of depression and anxiety on all scales used in the study.

It should be noted that a number of nosological forms of malignant tumors and crippling surgical interventions used in these diseases, such as enucleation of the eye, removal of the obturator apparatus of the rectum, breast extirpation lead to the deepest physical, psychological and social disability of patients. Laryngeal cancer is one of these localizations of the oncological process.

A very interesting and important study on this subject was carried out by Millgård M., Tuomi L. [13]. The study aimed to investigate the short-term and long-term effects of voice rehabilitation in patients treated with radiotherapy for laryngeal cancer as measured by both the acoustic measure smoothed cepstral peak prominence (CPPS) and perceptual measures. A secondary aim was to investigate the relationship between acoustic and perceptual measures. In total, 37 patients received voice rehabilitation post-radiotherapy and 37

patients constituted the irradiated control group. Outcome measures were mean CPPS for connected speech and ratings with the auditory-perceptual Grade, Roughness, Breathiness, Asthenia and Strain (GRBAS) scale. Outcome measures were analyzed 1 (baseline), 6, 12, and 24 months post-radiotherapy, where voice rehabilitation was conducted between the first two time-points. Additional recordings were acquired from vocally healthy participants for comparison. As a result, CPPS values of the voice rehabilitation group and vocally healthy group were not significantly different at 24 months post-radiotherapy. Ten out of 19 patients who received voice rehabilitation yielded a CPPS value above the threshold for normal voice 24 months post-radiotherapy, compared to 11 out of 26 in the irradiated control group. No statistically significant correlations were found between CPPS and perceptual parameters of GRBAS. Based on the results obtained, the authors conclude that voice rehabilitation for irradiated laryngeal cancer patients may have positive effects on voice quality up to 24 months post-radiotherapy. The relationship between CPPS and GRBAS as well as the applicability of CPPS for evaluation over several points of measurement needs to be studied further.

In their paper, Zhu X. et al. [14] emphasize that dysphagia is a common complication in patients with laryngeal cancer after surgery and radiotherapy. The aim of the study was to study the impact of swallowing training administered in combination with nutritional intervention on the nutritional status and quality of life of laryngeal cancer patients with dysphagia after surgery and radiotherapy. Sixty-six patients with laryngeal cancer who developed dysphagia were randomly divided into control group and intervention group (n = 33 in each group). Patients in both groups received total laryngectomy and prophylactic radiotherapy and were provided routine health counseling and swallowing training. Patients in the intervention group were additionally provided with nutritional intervention. All patients were evaluated using video fluoroscopic swallowing examination (VFSE), Patient-Generated Subjective Global Assessment on nutritional status (PG-SGA) score, and Quality of Life Questionnaire-core 30 (QLQ-c30) score immediately after radiotherapy and 3 months later. The results were as follows: prior to swallowing training, there was no significant between-group difference with respect to VFSE evaluation, PG-SGA score, or QLQ-c30 score. Both groups showed improvement in these measures at 3 months after radiotherapy; however, the improvement in the intervention group was significantly better than that in the control group. The researchers conclude that swallowing training combined with nutritional intervention can improve swallowing function, nutritional status and the quality of life of laryngeal cancer patients with dysphagia after operation and radiotherapy.

As noted by Salerno G. et al. [15], total laryngectomy represents the surgical procedure necessary for the treatment of some advanced neoplasms of the hypopharyngeal-laryngeal district and involves strong functional, physical and emotional repercussions. In their study, our colleagues examined how rehabilitation techniques used to improve the communication needs

of patients who have undergone laryngectomy affect their perception of quality of life. The questionnaires "V-RQoL" and "SECEL" were administered to 45 patients divided into four groups on the basis of the type of vicarious voice: group TE (27 patients), group E (7 patients), group EL (2 patients), group NV (9 patients). Patients using electrical or tracheo-esophageal prostheses reported a better quality of life than patients with an erythrophonic voice. Regarding postoperative satisfaction, the group with esophageal voice was the most satisfied. The authors emphasize the importance of preoperative counseling to make the patient as aware as possible of his future condition.

Retinoblastoma is an intraocular cancer of infancy and childhood, which has been treated with radiation therapy and chemotherapy. Radiation on growing patients can cause deterioration in maxillofacial growth and development that leads to severe skeletal discrepancies between the maxilla and mandible, and dental problems such as crossbite, openbite, and hypodontia. Kim S.H. et al. [16] presented a case of a 19-year-old Korean man with chewing disability and dentofacial deformities. He had undergone enucleation of the right eye and radiation therapy of the left eye due to retinoblastoma 100 days after birth. Subsequently, he received cancer therapy for the secondary nasopharyngeal cancer at the age of 11 years. He was diagnosed with severe skeletal deformity including sagittal, transverse, and vertical growth deficiency of the maxilla and midface, and with class III malocclusion, severe anterior and posterior crossbite, posterior openbite, multiple missing upper incisors, right premolars, and second molars, and impaction of the lower right second molars. To restore impaired functions and esthetics of the jaw and dentition, the orthodontic treatment combined with two jaw surgery was performed. At the end of surgical orthodontics, dental implants were placed for prosthetic treatment of missing teeth. Additional plastic surgery for zygoma elevation was done with calvarial bone graft followed by fat graft. Facial esthetics and occlusal functions of patient were favorably enhanced with the improvement of skeletal discrepancy and the rehabilitation of maxillary dentition by prosthetic work. At the 2-year follow-up, the skeletal and dental relationships and implant prosthetics were well maintained. The authors conclude as follows: in an adult patient with dentofacial deformities caused by early cancer therapy in the head and neck area, interdisciplinary interventions including additional plastic surgery of zygoma depression and prosthetic work of missing teeth as well as surgical-orthodontic treatment could establish favorable facial esthetics and oral rehabilitation.

The case of eyeball prosthetics was presented in their study by Goiato M.C. et al. [17]. Male patient, 60 years old, sought care at the Oral Oncology Center of the São Paulo State University "Júlio de Mesquita Filho", for the rehabilitation of the orbital cavity with an acrylic eye prosthesis. This prosthesis was made with thermopolymerizable acrylic resin and hand painted iris with oil paint on cardboard. The prosthesis was installed after finishing and polishing and the hygiene and general care instructions were explained. Colleagues focus on the fact that the lack of an eye has

an immediate and long-term impact on a patient's life. In the present case, the patient was satisfied with the aesthetics and comfort of the prosthesis, which demonstrates the success of the treatment.

As Rokohl A.C. et al. [18] show, a smooth supply with a visually appealing prosthetic eye after enucleation is not just a cosmetic solution, it is also a key factor in successful social and psychological rehabilitation. The authors submitted an overview of the current state of medical and ocular care regarding prosthetic eyes in Germany. It focuses mainly on the newest clinical results, daily care, complications, and psychological aspects of wearing prosthetic eyes. As a result of the latest clinical data and a current review of the PubMed literature, it was found that in Germany, enucleated patients normally get a double-walled, hollow prosthetic eye made of cryolite glass, and patients with a microphthalmic or phthisic eye receive a thin single-walled prosthesis. Anophthalmic patients wearing cryolite glass prosthetic eyes seem to be more satisfied with their appearance and the look of their prostheses than polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) prosthetic eye wearers. Cryolite glass prosthetic eyes must be renewed at least each year, while PMMA prostheses need to be polished once a year and renewed after five years of wearing. Among children, the fit of the prosthetic eye must be checked, based on growth, semi-annually. A slightly higher risk of breakage of cryolite glass prostheses is, for most patients, not a great disadvantage in everyday life. Ocularists and ophthalmologists should determine an individual cleaning regime, together with the patient, that is dependent on the material of the ocular prosthesis and other external factors. Complications, such as allergic, giant papillary, viral and bacterial conjunctivitis and blepharoconjunctivitis sicca must be treated at an early stage to allow for a prosthetic eye. In the case of inflammation-caused socket shrinkage or post-enucleation socket syndrome, surgical interventions are needed to re-enable the use of a prosthetic eye. Since the health of the remaining eye is the major psychological burden of prosthetic eye wearers, good ophthalmological care and medical screenings are essential elements. In conclusion, the researchers conclude that a smooth supply with a prosthetic eye, adequate and early treatment of possible complications and attention to psychological aspects is essential for successful long-term rehabilitation of enucleated patients.

As well as patients with previous localizations of the oncological process, patients with colorectal cancer with colostomies need mandatory rehabilitation measures.

Thus, Yang P. et al. [19] set themselves the goal of to systematically evaluate the effect of collaborative nursing on self-care ability of postcolostomy patients with colorectal cancer (CRC). PubMed, Web of Science, Embase, China National Knowledge Infrastructure, and Wanfang databases were searched to collect relevant literatures on randomized controlled trials of postcolostomy patients with CRC. The search period was started from 2010 to 2021. Statistical analysis was performed on the data extracted from the comprehensive meta-analysis with STATA 16.0 analysis software. As a result, it was found that the incidence of adverse

reactions in the control group was higher than that in the treatment group. Seven studies included the preintervention self-care concept and preintervention self-care skills. Six studies included preintervention self-care responsibility and preintervention exercise of self-care agency (ESCA) scale. In the comparison among the concept of self-care after intervention, self-care skills, self-care responsibility, and ESCA scale, all of them had higher scores in the treatment group than in the control group ($p < 0.05$). It fully explains that collaborative nursing can significantly improve the evaluation indicators of patients' self-care ability and reduce patient complications. In summary, the authors conclude that the application of collaborative nursing in the nursing work of patients with CRC after colostomy can significantly reduce the incidence of adverse nursing reactions.

The aim of the work is Yu S., Tang Y. [20] to explore the impacts of comprehensive care on psychological emotion, postoperative rehabilitation and complications of colorectal cancer patients after colostomy. From August 2018 to February 2020, a total of sixty colorectal cancer patients undergoing colostomy in our hospital were collected and randomly assigned to a control group to receive conventional care and a research group to receive comprehensive care, with 30 patients in each group. The two groups of patients were compared for postoperative recovery, complications, adverse psychological emotions, self-care ability, quality of life, and nursing satisfaction. The first time of exhaust, food intake and the recovery of bowel sound in the research group were markedly earlier than those in the control group. Besides, the research group had notably lower incidence of postoperative complications, lower self-anxiety scale (SAS) and self-depression scale (SDS) scores at discharge, and higher average self-care ability than the control group, as well as higher quality of life score and nursing satisfaction. At the end of the work, it was concluded that comprehensive care intervention can promote postoperative recovery of colorectal cancer patients after colostomy, relieve their negative emotions, reduce postoperative complications, improve quality of life and nursing satisfaction, which are all important and make this type of care worthy of promotion in clinical practice.

A study by Wang S.Y. et al. [21] examined the effects of a multimedia patient education intervention on improving self-care knowledge and skills in patients with colorectal cancer who underwent colostomy surgery. A quasi-experimental design was adopted to measure the self-care knowledge and skills of patients with colorectal cancer before and after surgery. The experimental group ($n = 33$) received a multimedia patient education intervention, whereas the control group ($n = 30$) was provided conventional instructions. Results were evaluated using analysis of covariance. On the day prior to discharge from hospital, the experimental group exhibited significantly greater improvement in self-care knowledge than did the control group. The experimental group also exhibited significantly greater improvement in self-care skills than did the control group on the day of gas passage, the day prior to dis-

charge from hospital, and during the first clinic visit after discharge from the hospital. In other words, multimedia patient education intervention yielded greater improvement in self-care knowledge and skills than did conventional instruction. The authors state that multimedia patient education is an adequate educational tool for patients with colorectal cancer who have undergone colostomy.

Now, regarding the rehabilitation of patients with breast cancer.

The leading method of treating malignant neoplasms, including breast cancer, is surgical. As Chan K.S. points out. et al. [22], functional results are increasingly important in breast cancer, as survival and prognosis for this pathology improve over the years. Since more than half of diagnosed breast cancer cases occur in middle-aged women between 45 and 64 years of age, it is appropriate to ensure preservation of upper extremity function as this group of patients may be the primary caregivers for their families, lead active lifestyles, and are at the peak of their careers. Additionally, most previous studies have shown that Asians may have higher body fat percentages, lower bone mass, and lower levels of physical activity than Western populations. These factors may influence functional outcomes in patients with breast cancer. The authors conducted a single-center prospective cohort study with a follow-up period of 6 weeks after surgery. The main inclusion criteria were patients over 21 years of age who underwent 44 radical surgical interventions - wide sectoral resection - 16 (36.4%) and mastectomy - 28 (63.6%). The main exclusion criteria were patients with pre-existing neurological or rheumatological comorbidities affecting upper limb function, or previous trauma that resulted in upper limb deformity. Patients who had undergone mastectomy with reconstruction were also excluded. The patients underwent early rehabilitation from the 1st day after surgery, including a standardized set of exercises for the shoulders and upper extremities. Active shoulder flexion and abduction range of motion and disability scores were assessed 1 week before surgery and then at weeks 2 and 6 postoperatively. This pilot study in an Asian cohort showed that patients were able to regain active range of motion of shoulder flexion and abduction at 6 weeks postoperatively, but had a worse disability score, especially in the axillary lymph node dissection subgroup after sentinel lymph node examination. Recommendations include the use of active early rehabilitation methods for breast cancer patients, however, as the authors note, longer follow-up is required to assess long-term functional results.

The modern direction in medical rehabilitation of patients with breast cancer, as well as in their treatment today, is the individualization of the treatment and rehabilitation program. As Olsson Möller U. et al. note in their publication [23], it is well known that women suffer from the negative consequences of breast cancer treatment and that their very important needs during rehabilitation interventions are often not met. At the same time, up to 43% of these women are at risk of developing chronic distress, requiring comprehensive treatment. However, it is unknown how to identify and meet the needs of these women early, leaving them with a

low chance of optimal rehabilitation. The authors plan to conduct a three-arm randomized controlled trial and aim to develop a model and evaluate the effect of individualized screening-based rehabilitation after primary treatment for breast cancer. The rehabilitation program will be based on self-reported data, focusing on physical and psychological outcomes, as well as treatment satisfaction at baseline at 2 weeks, 3, 6, 9 and 12 months. The assessment will also include economic aspects of health, based on register data and information from patients and their relatives during the rehabilitation process. In addition, optimal threshold levels of negative behaviors will be explored as an indicator of the need for extended rehabilitation. It is planned to identify potential new problems and rehabilitation needs of patients during the 1-year follow-up period. The researchers note that this study will provide important knowledge regarding the effectiveness of screening to identify needs for individualized, standardized, evidence-based rehabilitation after primary breast cancer treatment.

Much work regarding the development of a rehabilitation program for patients with breast cancer has been carried out by Spanish scientists and clinicians Barnadas A. et al. [24]. As the researchers emphasize, the gradual increase in incidence associated with the aging population and the implementation of screening programs, together with lower mortality rates from breast cancer, has led to an increase in the number of surviving patients with this pathology. The treatment used leaves physical, psychological and psychosocial consequences that can manifest and persist even years after completion of treatment and can interfere with the well-being of breast cancer patients and their reintegration into normal social and professional activities. Complications of the underlying disease and concomitant pathology require joint monitoring by specialized medical institutions and primary health care services. The authors have compiled guidelines aimed at ensuring joint and coordinated monitoring of these patients by these medical services. The guideline addresses health problems arising from treatment, with recommendations for a therapeutic approach that individualizes treatment, as well as suggestions for coordinated joint monitoring by primary and secondary care. In addition to organizational issues, the guide provides general recommendations for breast cancer patients: 1) avoid excess weight, 2) healthy diet and exercise, 3) quit smoking, 4) moderate alcohol consumption, 5) possible use of additional treatment methods, for example, such as acupuncture, 6) awareness of symptoms indicating a possible relapse or recurrent tumor, 7) adherence to prescribed anti-estrogenic hormone therapy for a long period (5-10 years), 8) return to work.

In addition, one of the modern methods of restorative treatment of cancer patients includes a method such as neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES) [25]. It may be a pragmatic short-term alternative to voluntary exercise in patients who are currently undergoing or have recently completed treatment for cancer. In this study, the authors assessed the impact of a personalized and progressive NMES exercise intervention, designed with the early rehabilitation period in mind,

on patients' physical performance and quality of life. This manipulation was found to improve performance on the 30-second sitting test (STS), the 6-minute walking test (6 MW), and global quality of life using the EORTC QLQ C-30 questionnaire. Benefits gained included improved muscle strength and greater confidence when walking. The authors recommend further evaluation of this technique in a further controlled prospective study.

In recent years, the term “multimodal” has been increasingly used in clinical research, which means, according to Wiktionary, involving or using several methods or modes of implementation. When analyzing a review of the literature related to multimodal rehabilitation of cancer patients, it should be noted that the overwhelming number of scientific works are devoted to the use of rehabilitation measures at the stage of preparing patients for specialized treatment, be it surgery or courses of drug or radiation therapy.

Guinan E.M. et al. [26] note in their work that the inflammatory changes themselves and the disruption of redox processes after radical surgery for esophageal cancer significantly affect both the quality of life and the survival of patients. In this regard, an integrated approach to the rehabilitation of these patients, including special exercises and a certain diet, can reduce the negative manifestations of the treatment. However, the authors note that the results will be further examined in a larger randomized controlled trial. In addition to the impact of these manifestations on the survival of patients, the economic side of the full rehabilitation of these patients will also be studied.

Bolshinsky V. et al. [27], based on an analysis of studies on multimodal rehabilitation programs before surgery for gastrointestinal tumors, conducted a systematic literature search using Medline, PubMed, Embase, Cinahl, Cochrane and Google Scholar databases. Study quality was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool (randomized trials) and the Newcastle-Ottawa Quality Assessment Scale (cohort studies). Of the 544 studies identified, 20 were included in the qualitative analysis. The authors found that although small studies have found encouraging results, larger prospective studies using uniform objective risk stratification and structured interventions with prespecified clinical and economic endpoints are needed to determine the definitive value of prehabilitation programs.

Summing up the analyzed works on rehabilitation measures in cancer patients with various nosological forms of malignant neoplasms, we can draw a definite conclusion that a multifaceted approach is required when conducting rehabilitation treatment in these patients, aimed at compensating for impaired body functions, improving the quality of life, reducing the severity of disability and prolonging active life. The process of recreating the vital status of patients is multidimensional and requires an integrated approach to restore the physical, psycho-emotional and social conditions of patients. At the same time, almost all authors agree on one thing: further multicenter randomized studies are needed to develop standardized approaches to conducting rehabilitation measures in cancer patients.

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